

**UNIVERSITAS STUDIORUM FLUMINENSIS
SVEUČILIŠTE U RIJECI**

uniri

**University of Rijeka Reform of Research
Assessment
– CoARA Action Plan 2024–2027 –**

Rijeka, December 2023

Introduction

In the quest to recognise the diverse contributions of its constituents and staff to all the academic activities, thus contributing to the European initiatives of reforming the research assessment system, in the summer of 2022 the [University of Rijeka, Croatia \(UNIRI\)](#) was one of the early signatories of the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment \(ARRA\)](#), hence officially joining the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#) and endorsing the respective commitments. In this framework, **UNIRI aims to reform the assessment of all academic activities, i.e., those including not merely research activities and outputs, but also teaching/supervision, leadership, community engagement and knowledge valorisation as well as societal (incl. cultural) and economic impact in general, and public outreach.**

In this document UNIRI lays down the activities it will implement in the short and medium timeframes to enhance its academic assessment approaches and practices.

Vision and mission

In its [Strategy 2021–2025](#), UNIRI defines its **vision** of becoming a **European University of the future** and its **mission** to conduct scientific, artistic, and development research, engaging its staff:

- as **teachers**, who prepare students for the jobs of the future and civic responsibility;
- as **researchers**, who open and empower the University by boldly embarking on innovative research ventures and collaborations to develop the economy and improve the well-being of the local community; and
- as **citizens**, who sincerely believe in the European values of freedom, human rights, and enlightenment, and are building a new European future;

relying in this framework on the following **values**:

- **responsibility** – we believe that institutional autonomy, academic integrity, academic freedom, and the pursuit of excellence and creativity in science and the arts are the prerequisites of authentic and quality achievements;
- **openness** – we nurture curiosity, courage, inclusiveness, diversity, participation, and solidarity as necessary conditions for progressive and just institutions;
- **innovation** – we recognize the importance of sustainable development, community engagement, education for the needs of the labour market and jobs of the future, and knowledge transfer as the pillars of social trust in academic institutions;
- **connection** – we cooperate in and encourage all forms of international relationships to promote the European values of peace, enlightenment, and harmonious relations.

UNIRI's **strategic objectives** are defined herein in four strategic areas within which the respective **quantitative and qualitative development goals** are defined:

- **learning and teaching** – promoting open education;
- **research** – promoting innovation and the development of the economy and community;
- **regional involvement** – promoting knowledge transfer and social responsibility for sustainable development; and
- **internationalization** – promoting the continuous expansion of horizons and strategic partnerships,

all within the **overarching objectives** of being internationally recognized as an open and modern European University that extends beyond the walls of institutions, research disciplines, and borders; one that continuously expands the horizons of sustainable development and

development of competitive innovation ecosystems, and one that enhances all citizens' quality of life and work while advancing the community's resilience and well-being in cooperation with the local and regional government.

The UNIRI research assessment reform action plan defined in this document is in line with these values and goals.

Current status

The existing research assessment framework at UNIRI is **bound chiefly by national legislation**, in particular the renewed Act on Higher Education and Scientific Activity adopted in October 2022, as well as the new Act on Quality Assurance in Higher Education and Science adopted in December 2022. This legal framework does provide a rather broad spectrum of elements for the assessment of research performing organisations (RPOs – higher education institutions, i.e., universities, faculties, research institutes and universities of applied science) and researchers themselves. In fact, in line also with the provisions of the European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education (ENQA), the RPOs are peer-reviewed assessed based on their:

- internal structure, employees and strategies;
- infrastructure and finances;
- quality assurance system;
- tracking and improvement of teaching;
- scientific productivity;
- professional work;
- other activities.

On the other hand, the academic staff is assessed based on **National criteria for employment to scientific-teaching, artistic-teaching, research and teaching positions**, which is still in course of revision, but it is in essence based on:

- **teaching contribution** (number of teaching hours held, supervision of students and PhDs, co-authorships with supervised students, authored textbooks, innovation of teaching methods, review of teaching curricula, specialisations in teaching profession via international mobility, production of open teaching material, participation to life-long teaching activities, teaching in foreign languages);
- **research and professional contribution** (number and ranking of authored publications, presentations of scientific publications and work, invited and keynote lectures, scientific books, open science practices, scientific and professional projects, editorial of scientific journals and proceedings, participation to organisation of scientific and professional conferences, peer-review activities, knowledge transfer projects and activities, innovations, outreach activities);
- **contribution to society and the institutional profile** (leadership functions, institutional development projects, membership in international and national bodies, awards and similar).

Despite the quite exhaustive breadth of the above criteria, they are **still based almost exclusively on quantitative metrics**, and therefore fail to address the broadly established shortcomings in assessing, recognising, incentivising and rewarding the true quality and impact of all the diverse and multifaceted valuable contribution of the national RPOs and the academic and other staff involved in all the various academic activities.

With the aim of addressing these shortcomings, in the last few years the management of UNIRI has, therefore, strongly oriented its efforts towards **promoting a cultural shift towards qualitative**

and socially accountable research assessment initiatives and approaches, with the resulting enhancement of responsible, equitable, transparent, efficient and sustainable assessment practices, promoting in this framework also open science measures. UNIRI has, in particular, actively joined and contributed to the following **international commitments, guidelines, initiatives and projects**:

- The [Young Universities for the Future of Europe \(YUFE\) European University alliance](#), with its numerous activities related to research assessment, and in particular:
 - the partnership in the [YUFE Transforming R&I Through Europe-Wide Knowledge Transfer \(YUFERING\)](#) Horizon 2020 project, which co-created, within the project's WP4, a joint [YUFE Competence Framework for Researchers](#), whose elements, including candidates' narrative CV, are already partly implemented in the [Yufe4Postdocs](#) project co-funded by the Horizon Europe's Marie Skłodowska-Curie programme;
 - the partnership in the [Developing and Implementing hands-on training on Open Science and Open Innovation for Early Career Researchers \(DIOSI\)](#) Horizon 2020 project that successfully developed measures and practices of enhancing the skills of doctoral students that will allow them to initiate entrepreneurial activities, as well as of acquiring knowledge on open science.
- The [Young European Research Universities Network \(YERUN\)](#), involved in various academic researcher assessment activities and initiatives.
- UNIRI signed in 2021 the [San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment \(DORA\)](#).
- UNIRI is an early signatory of the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment \(ARRA\)](#), thus joining in 2022 the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#) and endorsing the respective commitments. Currently UNIRI is actively involved and is contributing to two CoARA working groups (WGs), i.e., the WG on "Reforming Academic Career Assessment (ACA)" and the WG "Early-and-mid-Career Researchers (EMCRs) – Assessment and Research Culture".
- [Human Researcher Strategy for Researchers \(HRS4R\)](#): UNIRI was among the first European institutions that endorsed the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the recruitment of Researchers, earning already in 2010 the HRS4R Excellence in Research logo. Currently UNIRI is in the process of renewing this recognition, while aligning with the open, transparent and merit-based (OTM-R) practices and the provision of the newly proposed Charter for Researchers, with its revised principles.
- Partnership in the [Open and Universal Science \(OPUS\)](#) Horizon Europe project, whose main goal is to develop activities related to the reform of research assessment so as to enhance and promote the application of open science practices. In this framework, UNIRI is one of the RPOs that will be piloting the proposed interventions, indicators and metrics.
- Partnership in the [Sustainable Careers for Researcher Empowerment \(SECURE\)](#) Horizon Europe project aiming at creating, trialling, implementing, and mainstreaming a research career framework to support organisations in the recruitment, employment, training, development, progression, and mobility of researchers, while improving research careers and reducing career precarity, where again UNIRI is one of the RPOs piloting the proposed activities.

In addition, UNIRI's strong commitment and determination towards redefining its research assessment procedures and criteria is reflected in the following **institutional documents, policies and practices**:

- The determinants of the **Strategy of the University of Rijeka for the period from 2021 to 2025**, where **quantitative key performance indicators (KPIs) are accompanied by**

qualitative ones.

- [UNIRI Open Science Policy](#), developing on UNIRI's early "Declaration on Open Science" accepted already in January 2019 (as the first in Croatia and one of the first in the EU), and adopted by the University Senate in September 2021.
- Recommendations from the session of the [UNIRI International Scientific Council](#) of the University, held on November 15, 2021 (internal).
- Conclusions from the 4th joint thematic session of the [UNIRI Senate](#) and the Council of the University of Rijeka on the topic "State and perspectives of the development of science at the University of Rijeka" held on July 12, 2022 (internal), stressing, among others, the need to develop institutional career assessment criteria, a strong focus of this assessment on quality and the promotion of the flexibilization of the standardised working duties as well as open science practices.
- [Guidelines for the additional \(institutional\) criteria for the selection of scientific-teaching, artistic-teaching, teaching, associate and professional staff at the University of Rijeka and its constituents](#) adopted by the UNIRI Senate in September 2023. The herein set criteria, to be eventually adapted by each UNIRI constituent to the respective scientific discipline and its institutional strategies and policies, as well as to the career development stage of the single planned employment positions, recommends the introduction of narrative-based CVs and, under the assumption that any single researcher cannot excel in all the defined areas and practices, encompass the assessment of:
 - **academic skills:** quality of publications, knowledge of research methodologies, multi-, inter- and trans-disciplinarity in research activities, internationalisation, usage of open science principles and practices, teaching skills, management of research, peer review, financing, community engagement;
 - **skills related to academic and institutional behaviour:** professionalism, leadership, institutional policies, contributions to United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) / European Research Area / European Higher Education Area principles and actions, teamwork, communication skills;
 - **personal qualities and skills:** basic disciplinary knowledge, enthusiasm, persistence, integrity, self-confidence, responsibility, adaptability, conflict resolution, cognitive abilities, career development (incl. mobility), management of own resources, creativity, understanding of societal and cultural contexts.
- In all the above activities, **particular attention is dedicated to UNIRI's early career researchers (ECRs - doctoral candidates and postdocs)**, so that UNIRI is also tailoring several specific ECR policies and practices such as:
 - establishment of the **UNIRI Doctoral School**, functionally integrating and coordinating the activities of all the UNIRI doctoral study programs as well as promoting in this framework quality, interdisciplinarity and internationalisation as well as the development of transversal skills of the doctoral candidates;
 - specific criteria for the selection of ECR supervisors and the monitoring of their work (including feedback of the ECRs);
 - measures of monitoring and improving the success of ECRs' career progression.
- What is more, in all its process, including those related to research assessment, UNIRI **strongly fosters non-discrimination** in any way on the basis of gender, age, ethnic, national or social origin, religion or belief, sexual orientation, language, disability, political opinion, social or

economic condition (cf. the [UNIRI Code of Ethics](#)) and promotes gender equality. In fact, UNIRI is the first university in Croatia to have adopted the [Gender Equality Plan 2021-2025](#), with one of the four strategic areas being Gender equality in scientific and artistic research. In this framework UNIRI was part of the [Supporting and Implementing Plans for gender Equality in Academia and Research \(SPEAR\)](#) Horizon 2020 project and, through the activities coordinated by its [Gender Equality Council](#), developed, among others:

- the [Recommendation for improving gender balance in appointments](#), the [Guidelines on gender inclusive communication](#), the [A safe place without sexual harassment](#) guidelines and the [Policy statement on the prevention of and protection against sexual harassment](#),
- the [Guidelines for balancing business and private life of employed parents/carers at the University of Rijeka](#), and the respective [Recommendations for ensuring the balance between professional and private life of working parents](#).

It should be also emphasized that all UNIRI's procedures are herein aligned not only with national, but also with international (ILO, EU, WEF) regulations and policy documents. UNIRI policies are also part of and aligned with the [YUFE Diversity and Inclusivity Strategy](#) and the [YERUN 2021 - 2025 Strategic plan entitled "Enabling talent to grow"](#).

- Last but not least, UNIRI is also very active and contributes to the development of its **research management capacities**, especially those of the [University Centre for Research and Innovation](#), which encompasses also the recently established [Pre-Award Research Support Centre](#). In this framework it is very active in the [EARMA European Association of Research Managers and Administrators](#), as well as in the associated [BESTPRAC network](#).

Key challenges

Besides the mentioned **centralised national research and academic assessment system**, that strongly influences and limits the institutional autonomy in a more pronounced quality- and impact-oriented reform of these fields, the key challenge is the fact that the **UNIRI constituents**, i.e., its faculties, **are mostly legal entities on their own**, whose self-sufficiency has been even strengthened by the above-mentioned new Act on Higher Education and Scientific Activity. This means that at the University level only coordination and support measures and guidelines can be introduced, whereas their practical implementation at the constituents is ultimately voluntary. The below given actions and the respective timeframes are thus to be understood as those that will be fostered, incentivised and concerted via the instruments (including financial ones) at the disposal at the University level. The UNIRI management will herein also promote institutional capacity building and awareness raising, including the exchange of good practices with the various partner universities both nationally and internationally, but also among the UNIRI constituents.

Action plan

Based on the boundary conditions described above, UNIRI defines herein its actions to be performed towards quality-based, accountable as well as socially and economically impact-driven academic assessment, the connection with the respective CoARA commitments, the respective timeframes, and the responsible institutional actors. In the short term, many coherent and intertwined activities are hence planned to lead then, via the foreseen midterm activities, including iterative reviewing and revision phases, to gradual changes in the UNIRI institutional, project and individual academic staff and team assessment practices across all the institutional processes, having also in mind the evidenced nationally-defined framework.

ACTIONS IN THE SHORT TERM (UP TO THE END OF 2024)	RELATED CoARA COMMITMENTS	TIMEFRAME	RESPONSIBILITY*
Publicly share this Action Plan on the UNIRI website and via other UNIRI communication channels	All	Q1 2024	Vice-rector for Strategic Projects and Head of UNIRI R&I Centre
Actively promote and advocate the UNIRI Guidelines for the additional (institutional) criteria for the selection of scientific-teaching, artistic-teaching, teaching, associate and professional staff at the University of Rijeka and its constituents as well as the related UNIRI Rulebook on Scientific, Artistic and Innovation Activities, thus further promoting academic assessment that is open, transparent, focused on qualitative evaluation, ethical, respecting equality and non-discrimination, based on reliable data, and customized for various areas of science and arts, as well as the adaptable to the diverse needs of the UNIRI constituents	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Recognise the diversity of contributions 2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation 6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes 7. Raise awareness of reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training 8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning 9. Communicate progress 	Continuously throughout 2024	UNIRI management, especially the Vice-rector for Strategic Projects and the Vice-rector for Science and Arts
Actively participate in the activities of the CoARA WG on “Reforming Academic Career Assessment (ACA)”, especially as a pilot organisation filling in and giving feedback on the survey within Task 1.1 <i>Mapping existing initiatives</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes 7. Raise awareness of reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training 8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning 9. Communicate progress 10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid 	Continuously throughout 2024 / Q1 2024	Vice-rector for Strategic Projects and Head of UNIRI R&I Centre

	evidence, and make data openly available		
Analyse the results of the gap analysis, revise and update the respective Action Plan with clear timeframe and responsibilities and resubmit the application for the HRS4R Excellence in Research logo	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Recognise the diversity of contributions 2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation 5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment 6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes 7. Raise awareness of reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training 8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning 9. Communicate progress 10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence, and make data openly available 	Q1 2024	UNIRI management
Adopt the UNIRI Artificial Intelligence Policy	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment 6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes 10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence, and make data openly available 	Q1 2024	UNIRI management and Senate, UNIRI Centre for Artificial Intelligence and Cybersecurity as well as newly appointed AI expert body
Adopt the updated UNIRI Regulations on Doctoral Study Programmes and support the activities of the UNIRI Doctoral School	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Recognise the diversity of contributions 6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes 	Q1 2024 / continuously throughput 2024	UNIRI management and Senate, Vice-rector for Science and Arts Head of

			Doctoral School with Expert Council of doctoral School
Pilot the elements of the YUFE Competence Framework for Researchers, including the adoption of the narrative CVs, in the practical execution of the employment of the 2 nd cohort of the Yufe4postocs candidates, and exchange experiences with the other partner universities of the YUFE European University alliance	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Recognise the diversity of contributions 2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation 5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment 6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes 8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning 9. Communicate progress 	Q2 2024	Vice-rector for Science and Arts and Centre for Science and Arts
Revise and update the UNIRI Open Science Policy	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Abandon inappropriate uses of journal- and publication-based metrics 4. Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations 5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment 6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes 7. Raise awareness of reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training 8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning 9. Communicate progress 10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence, and make data openly available 	Q2 2024	UNIRI University Library, especially its Centre for the Promotion of Open Science (COZ)
Actively participate in and contribute to the proposal of the National criteria for the	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Recognise the diversity of contributions 6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, 	Q2 2024	UNIRI management

<p>employment to scientific-teaching, artistic-teaching, research and teaching positions</p>	<p>tools and processes 10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence, and make data openly available</p>		<p>(especially Rector and Vice-rector for Strategic Projects) and Senate</p>
<p>Collect data and analyse the UNIRI results for the chosen cohort of ECRs according to the developed Action plan in the OPUS HE project after the first interim evaluation of the chosen interventions (encompassing policy, resources, repository, awareness raising and training interventions with respective risk mitigation and initial rewarding measures), as well as indicators and metrics pertaining to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the research category (subcategory of publications/ publication drafting): Published Publications Openly Available, - the education category (subcategory of skills/ skills development): Open Science Skills Certificates Obtained, and - the valorisation category (subcategory of communication/ public speaking): Appearances Openly Available. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Recognise the diversity of contributions 2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation 3. Abandon inappropriate uses of journal- and publication-based metrics 5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment 6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes 7. Raise awareness of reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training 8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning 9. Communicate progress 10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence, and make data openly available 	<p>Q3 2024</p>	<p>UNIRI OPUS working group coordinated by the Vice-rector for Strategic Projects and with strong involvement of the UNIRI Faculty of Law, of the University Library and especially COZ, as well as of the Centre for Science Outreach (SOCRI)</p>
<p>Define the UNIRI interventions, indicators and metrics and develop the respective Action Plan of piloting activities pertaining to the Research Career Framework as well as to the Tenure Track-like Model as foreseen in the framework of the SECURE HE project; start the respective</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Recognise the diversity of contributions 2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation 5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment 6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes 	<p>Q3 2024</p>	<p>UNIRI SECURE working group coordinated by the Vice-rector for Strategic Projects</p>

implementation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. Raise awareness of reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training 8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning 9. Communicate progress 10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence, and make data openly available 		
Ensure access to suitable and easily accessible national Open Science repositories and raise awareness on the importance of Open Science	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment 6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes 	Q3 2024	UNIRI University Library and University of Rijeka Library System
Setup a fully functional UNIRI Centre for Science Outreach (SOCRI) online digital platform, thus providing a comprehensive online repository for archiving of outreach activities (e.g. public speaking appearances) as well as providing support and training in public outreach activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment 7. Raise awareness of reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training 10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence, and make data openly available 	Q3 2024	Head of SOCRI
Actively participate in and contribute to the activities of the CoARA WG on “Early-and-mid-Career Researchers (EMCRs) – Assessment and Research Culture”	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes 7. Raise awareness of reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training 8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning 9. Communicate progress 10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence, and make data openly available 	Continuously throughout 2024	Vice-rector for Strategic Projects and Head of UNIRI R&I Centre
Continue offering the trainings in Open Science and Open Innovation piloted via the DIOSI	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Recognise the diversity of contributions 5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment 	Continuously throughout 2024	UNIRI University Library and

project and other fora UNIRI is actively involved in, focused especially to UNIRI ECRs, thus raising their level of skills in these transversal areas of expertise	7. Raise awareness of reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training		University of Rijeka Library System as well as Science and Technology Park STEP RI
With the involvement of the UNIRI Doctoral School, develop training modules focused on peer-review good practices and skills (especially professionalism, integrity and ethical considerations as well as bias avoidance), and promote means to actively engage, guide and support ECRs in such trainings and the application of the thus acquired skills	2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation 3. Abandon inappropriate uses of journal- and publication-based metrics 5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment 6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes 7. Raise awareness of reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training 8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning	Continuously throughout 2024	Vice-rector for Science and Arts, Head of Doctoral School with Expert Council of doctoral School
Take active part in and contribute to the activities of the YUFE 2030 WP5 on Responsible, Interdisciplinary & Inclusive Research, and especially the task 5.1 “Research on responsible research assessment and development of joint policy framework”	All	Continuously throughout 2024	Vice-rector for Strategic Projects and Head of UNIRI R&I Centre
Take active part in and contribute to the activities of the YERUN WGs on Academic Careers, on CoARA, on Open Science and on Knowledge Valorisation	All	Continuously throughout 2024	Vice-rector for Strategic Projects
Continuously promote non-discrimination and gender equality in all assessment procedures	1. Recognise the diversity of contributions 6. Review and develop research assessment criteria,	Continuously throughout 2024	UNIRI Gender Equality Council,

	tools and processes 10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence, and make data openly available		Diversity officer and other involved bodies
Involve and seek feedback on the planned and performed RRA activities from the UNIRI University Council, the International Scientific Council, the Council for Science, the Expert Councils and other UNIRI expert committees, also with the aim to identify means to actively involve the UNIRI research staff in RRA and to incentivise, recognise and reward such involvement	All	Continuously throughout 2024	UNIRI Rector and management
Organise Open Science and PhD career Café's, Doctoral Days and other similar awareness raising activities and events aimed at promoting Open Science, ECRs' transversal competencies and RRA in general	1. Recognise the diversity of contributions 5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment 7. Raise awareness of reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training	Continuously throughout 2024	UNIRI University Library and Head of Doctoral School
Take active part in and contribute to the activities of the international fora for research assessment, as well as ERA, EHEA, EUA, EARMA and other policy fora	All	Continuously throughout 2024	UNIRI management
Continuously monitor the above activities and practices and transparently communicate on the UNIRI website to the internal and external research communities and other stakeholders the progress on the RRA	All	Continuously throughout 2024	Head of UNIRI R&I Centre

* Cf. the structure of the UNIRI management and of the decision-making, counselling and operative bodies provided on uniri.hr/en/about-university/structure/

MIDTERM ACTIONS (UP TO THE END OF 2027)	RELATED CoARA COMMITMENTS	TIMEFRAME	RESPONSIBILITY*
<p>Monitor, review and update the activities described in the 2024 plan pertaining to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the UNIRI non-discrimination, gender equality, Open Science, AI, outreach and other RRA-related plans and policies; - the ECRs-related activities of the UNIRI Doctoral School, University Library, Career Counselling Office and SOCRI ; - the UNIRI Guidelines for the additional (institutional) criteria for the selection of ... staff at the University of Rijeka and its constituents; - HRS4R and especially the OTM-R practices and the new Charter for Researchers; - UNIRI participation in the CoARA WGs on “Reforming Academic Career Assessment (ACA)” and on “Early-and-mid-Career Researchers (EMCRs) – Assessment and Research Culture”; - the UNIRI application of the YUFE Competence Framework for Researchers and the UNIRI participation in the YUFE 2030 WP5 activities on Responsible, Interdisciplinary & Inclusive Research; - UNIRI participation in the YERUN WGs on academic careers; 	<p>All</p>	<p>Continuously throughout 2025</p>	<p>UNIRI management (especially Rector, Vice-rector for Strategic Projects and Head of UNIRI R&I Centre) and Senate, with involvement of UNIRI University Council, the International Scientific Council, the Council for Science, the Expert Councils and other UNIRI expert committees</p>

<p>- UNIRI active participation in and contribution to other international fora for research assessment, ERA, EHEA, EUA, EARMA, ...</p>			
<p>Collect data and analyse the UNIRI results for the chosen cohort of ECRs according to the developed Action plan in the OPUS HE project after the second and final interim evaluation of the chosen interventions, indicators and metrics as described for 2024</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Recognise the diversity of contributions 2. Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation 3. Abandon inappropriate uses of journal- and publication-based metrics 5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment 6. Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes 7. Raise awareness of reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training 8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning 9. Communicate progress 10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence, and make data openly available 	<p>Q3 2025</p>	<p>UNIRI OPUS working group coordinated by the Vice-rector for Strategic Projects and with strong involvement of the UNIRI Faculty of Law, of the University Library and especially COZ, as well as of the Centre for Science Outreach (SOCRI)</p>
<p>Develop and implement, based on DIOSI, YUFERING, OPUS and other project outcomes, as well as on internal best practices, UNIRI training material for ECRs supervisors with the focus on ethics, networking, informing on counselling. Organise respective events, thus enhancing mentoring quality and facilitating peer learning</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. Raise awareness of reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training 8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning 	<p>Q3 2025</p>	<p>Head of UNIRI Doctoral School with Expert Council of doctoral School and UNIRI Career Counselling Office</p>
<p>Develop and implement on the SOCRI online digital platform a fully functional virtual SOCRI,</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Commit resources to reforming research assessment 7. Raise awareness of reform and provide transparent 	<p>Q3 2025</p>	<p>UNIRI OPUS working group</p>

<p>offering instructions for University constituents and academic staff on how to contribute to the outreach repository, complemented by a technical support system for video content creation</p>	<p>communication, guidance, and training</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning 9. Communicate progress 10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence, and make data openly available 		<p>coordinated by the Vice-rector for Strategic Projects, Head of Centre for Science Outreach (SOCRI)</p>
<p>Monitoring and ensuring user satisfaction in ECRs career and personal counselling services piloted on a chosen group of doctoral candidates, as well as informing all UNIRI PhD programs' coordinators about career counselling for doctoral candidates, thus supporting ECRs in challenges during and after their studies, but also in career management and better readiness for job market</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Recognise the diversity of contributions 7. Raise awareness of reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training 8. Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning 9. Communicate progress 10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence, and make data openly available 	<p>Q4 2025</p>	<p>Head of UNIRI Doctoral School with Expert Council of doctoral School and UNIRI Career Counselling Office</p>
<p>Produce a comprehensive interim evaluation report on the UNIRI RRA activities outlined above and publicly share this report, as well as the revised version of this Action plan, on the UNIRI website and via other UNIRI communication channels</p>	<p>All</p>	<p>End of 2025</p>	<p>Vice-rector for Strategic Projects and Head of UNIRI R&I Centre</p>
<p>Perform another iteration of monitoring, reviewing and updating the UNIRI RRA activities specified in the revised Action Plan as defined the end of 2025. Communicate regularly on the achieved progress</p>	<p>All</p>	<p>Continuously throughout 2026 and 2027</p>	<p>UNIRI management (especially Rector, Vice-rector for Strategic Projects and Head of UNIRI R&I Centre) and</p>

			Senate, with involvement of UNIRI University Council, the International Scientific Council, the Council for Science, the Expert Councils and other UNIRI expert committees
Produce a comprehensive final 5-year evaluation report on the UNIRI RRA activities and publicly share the resulting report on the UNIRI website and via other UNIRI communication channels	All	End of 2027	Vice-rector for Strategic Projects and Head of UNIRI R&I Centre

* Cf. the structure of the UNIRI management and of the decision-making, counselling and operative bodies provided on uniri.hr/en/about-university/structure/

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